

COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS OF CHICKPEA PLANT NODULATION UNDER DIFFERENT SOIL CONDITIONS

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Abstract: Over 800 million ha. of land throughout the world are salt-affected, either by salinity or the associated condition of sodicity. This is over 6% of the world's total land area. Most of this salinity, and all of the sodicity is natural. However, a significant proportion of recently cultivated agricultural land has become saline because of land clearing or irrigation. Chickpea (*Cicer arietinum L.*) is an annual, self-pollinated legume crop (Wang et al 2019) grown mainly in arid and semi-arid regions all over the world. It is the second most important legume crop and is a source of high quality nutrients.

Key words: legume, nodules, saline soil, arid soil, dry resistant, tolerant, salt lands, soil toxicity.

INTRODUCTION

The earliest written account of salt lands dates back to 2400 BC and was recorded in the Tigris–Euphrates alluvial plains of Iraq. Salinity destroyed the ancient societies that had successfully thrived for several centuries (Hillel 2005; Rengasamy 2006). (1) Saline soils can be found at different altitudes, from below sea level (e.g. around the Dead Sea) to mountains rising above 5,000 m, such as the Tibetan Plateau or the Rocky Mountains. Of nearly, 160 million ha. of cultivated land under irrigation worldwide, about one-third is already affected by salt, which makes salinity a major constraint to food production. It is the single largest soil toxicity problem in tropical Asia (Greenland 1984).

Over 800 million ha. of land throughout the world are salt-affected, either by salinity (397 million ha.) or the associated condition of sodicity (434 million ha.) (FAO 2005). This is over 6% of the world's total land area. Most of this salinity, and all of the sodicity is natural. However, a significant proportion of recently cultivated agricultural land has become saline because of land clearing or irrigation. Of the 1,500 million ha. of land farmed by dryland agriculture, 32 million (2%) are affected by secondary salinity to varying degrees. Of the current 230 million ha. of irrigated land,

45 million ha. are salt-affected (20%) (FAO 2005). Irrigated land is only 15% of total cultivated land, but as irrigated land has at least twice the productivity of rain-fed land, it produces one-third of the world's food (Munns 2005).(2)

Legumes (*Fabaceae*) are a diverse family with worldwide distribution and a broad range of plant forms. They are the second most important crop plant family after Poaceae and grain legumes (pulses) account for 27% of global crop production (Vance et al 2002), providing nutrition for millions of people. Legumes are considered to be a multipurpose crop, and can be used directly as food or in processed forms as a feed for livestock or as a rotation crop that improves soil health through nitrogen fixation (Merga et al 2019). Chickpea (*Cicer arietinum L.*) is an annual, self-pollinated legume crop (Wang et al 2019)grown mainly in arid and semi-arid regions all over the world. It is the second most important legume crop and is a source of high quality nutrients. Chickpea seeds are rich in protein (20–30%), with a considerable amount of essential amino acids (e.g., lysine, tyrosine, glu tamic acid and histidine), carbohydrates (up to 40%), minerals (e.g., phosphorus, calcium, magnesium, iron and zinc), vitamins (e.g.,-carotene) and fiber (Kudapa, H 2018)6. Chickpea, therefore, forms an essential part of a diet in developing countries. Moreover, farmers face climate change, a growing human population and demand for more high-quality crop food. Find ing the solution for these issues is very challenging, especially in the context of increasingly limited land and water resources (Merga et al 2019; Afshin, et al 2014; Shin,et al 2019)

Chickpea is the most important cool-season food legume and provides nutritional food to the growing population(Ahmed, S.M, et al 2021; Kaashyap, M et al 2018). With climate change, chickpea will become an increasingly important crop (Belluci et al 2021; Kumari, P et al 2020;,Rani et al 2020). Over the years, chickpea production has increased from 6.4 to 14.7 million tons due to its growing demand and economic viability (FAO.2021). However, salinity is a significant constraint that reduces chickpea production by 8-10 per cent at a global scale— a static which is increasingly alarming in the context of growing population and climate challenged food security (Atieno, J et al 2017; Kaashyap, M et al 2018, Kotula, L et al 2020 Atieno, J et al 2021).

Chickpea is intrinsically sensitive to salinity during the reproductive stages, affecting the crop yields (Ahmed, S.M, et al 2021; Khan,H.A et al 2015). It can withstand salinity up to an electrical conductivity (EC) value of less than or equal to 1.0 dS/m compared to cereals, which can tolerate up to an EC equal to 10.0 dS/m (Flowers T,J et al 2010). Considerable breeding efforts have been made to underpin the salt tolerance traits; however, confounding effects of abiotic stress during the field trials and the polygenic nature of salt stress have rendered these approaches inadequate to uncover the intricate nature of complex gene networks. The QTLs identified for salt tolerance traits do not span the major and minor genes underlying the salt tolerance molecular mechanisms (Bharadwaj, C et al 2021). Furthermore, due to continued

climatic shifts, these QTLs ought to be unstable and thus far could not be deployed in crop breeding programs to improve salt tolerance and develop new crop varieties.

Peas are valuable food, fodder, and a good companion crop for other crops, and are resistant to drought. For this reason, peas grow and develop well in dry lands and give a high yield. According to its biological characteristics, pea seeds germinate when the average temperature is +3-4 °C. Lawns can withstand frosts of 6-8 °C. M. Vaughn and Oppen (2019) studied the biological characteristics of peas and found that the height is 25-75 cm, the flower is of different colors, the number of grains in one pod is 1-3, and the grain is from black to yellow. recorded. As noted by I. Hamdamov and others(2018), they studied the flowering rhythm of some varieties of peas under irrigation and proved that the productivity is related to its flowering rhythm. S.B. Mustanov(2020) justified that if the moisture content of the soil is 60-70-60% in irrigated pea varieties, flowering will be normal, there will be many pods, and the yield will be high. In the experiments of K. Sangupta and R. Roy(2017), it was proved that when there is a lot of moisture, the germination process of peas goes well and the productivity is high. The yield of peas depends on the number of grains and the weight of 1000 grains. In the researches of K. Eshmirzaev(2021), it was proved that due to the high location of pea pods, the harvest is abundant. M.H. Mengesha, et al.(2018), under the conditions of India, the protein content of the grain is 18.62-25.80%, carbon water is 42.5-59.2%, and fat is 4.87-8.19%. noted that it will be up to According to N.N. Balashova(2019), peas do not require nitrogen fertilizers. V. Dahiya(2019) found out in his research that the more nitrogen the pea absorbs, the more its protein accumulates. According to P.Shukurullaev's(2021) experiments, he found out that the roots of peas in dry lands develop 2 meters deep and use less moisture due to the fact that there are few lateral roots..

Peas are more nutritious than most other leguminous crops and contain 20.1-32.4% protein. Peas contain a lot of phosphorus, potassium, magnesium elements, lecithin, riboflavin (vitamin B₂), nicotinic and panthenic acid, choline, and vitamin C. being rich in asparagine and glutamine amino acids, pea grain replaces 53 meats in the human consumption fund. For this reason, two-thirds of the peas grown in the world are consumed as food.

Among grain-legume crops, pea, which is resistant to drought and heat, is a valuable food and fodder crop that enriches the soil with biological nitrogen and increases its productivity, and is a crop resistant to drought, heat and cold. The period of growth and development of a pea plant is 90 to 110 days. Amino acids contained in peas are unique and distinguished by their ability to eliminate various harmful and pathological factors in the human body. Peas are more nutritious than most other leguminous crops and contain 20.1-32.4% protein. Peas have long been cultivated in the arid regions of Central and Asia Minor. No wild species found. It occupies the third

place among leguminous crops in terms of cultivated area. Cultivated area is 10 mln. including 8 mln. ha is cultivated in India. It is rarely planted in the dry lands of our country. At present, the technology of cultivation in wetlands is being researched. Productivity is 15-20 s/ha. Chickpea belongs to the genus *Cicer L.* and includes 31 species, 22 of which are perennial and widely distributed on the Mediterranean coast. Only one cultivated type of chickpea *Cicer arietinum L* is used. Common pea is an annual herb. The tap root is well developed, penetrates the soil up to 1-1.5 m, and is branched. The stem is strong, grows upright, branches well, becomes woody when mature, 15-40 cm high in dry land, 45-70 cm in wet land. The leaves are complex, oddly feathery, the number of pairs of short-banded leaves is 5-15, the leaves are small, saw-toothed, hairy. Feathers contain organic acids (calcic acid, malic acid). The leaves are light and dark green. The flowers are bisexual, placed one in the axils of small leaves, the color is white, red, pink, red purple. Pea is a self-pollinating plant, but in some cases it can be pollinated from outside. Pods are convex, cone-shaped or rhomboid, contain 1-3 seeds, 1.5-3.5 cm long, light yellow, brown in color. The stem, pods and leaves of the plant are hairy. The seed is round-shaped, has a beak, is round or angular in shape, the color is from light yellow to black, the weight of 1000 is 100-600 g. Pea is a self-pollinating plant. Pea is a heat-loving plant, but its seeds germinate at 3-5°C, and its grass can withstand frosts of -8-10°C. There are wintering forms in our country. Light-loving long-day plant. It is drought resistant among legumes. When there is a lot of moisture, it is more affected by ascochitosis. It does not choose the soil very well, it gives less yield in saline, low-fertility, sandy soils. Depending on the growing conditions and varieties, the growing period can be 65-140 days. Varieties: 125 varieties of "Milyutinsky-4", "Duragay-27", "Zimistoni", "Lazzat", "Uzbekiston-32", "Yulduz" are grown in our country.

Along with the issue of protein, growing peas helps to solve the problem of increasing grain production, increasing soil fertility, and provides environmentally friendly products (Atabayeva X.N et al 2018). All agricultural crops planted after leguminous crops have good results. Legumes can easily replace alfalfa on farms. First of all, they serve to improve soil fertility, and secondly, to provide the population with valuable, protein-rich products and livestock with nutritious fodder (Xoliqov B. Et al 2017). It is known that one of the main agrotechnological measures in the production of high-yield and high-quality seeds from pea varieties is the recovery of healthy lawns by planting seeds in the right time and in the right way. Because, among the factors affecting the growth, development, winter resistance and other factors of autumn planted peas, the period of autumn planting is important (Hamdamov I. et al 2007). In each region, the sowing of pea seeds in the fall should be carried out in optimal terms, depending on the soil and climate conditions, uniform collection of the seeds, good preparation for entering the winter rest period, and moderate wintering. ensures a high

yield. If the pea crop is planted too early for the region, the warm air temperatures and moisture in the soil in the fall will cause the plants to germinate, and as a result, the lawn will be damaged by the frosts that occur in the winter and before the early spring. Peas sown in late fall will overwinter in the pre-germination phase and germinate in early spring. When planted too late, i.e. in winter, the seeds may not germinate at all (Bobokulov Z.R, 2022, Bobomuradov Z.S, and Bobokulov Z.R. 2021). Nowadays, providing the population with food products has become one of the most important and urgent issues. Due to the increase in the number of people and the reduction of arable land, providing the population with food is becoming more difficult every year. It is known that we are paying special attention to the radical improvement of the meliorization of irrigated lands during the agricultural reform. This task has been and will remain one of the most important priorities. Because the efficiency of agricultural production, ensuring the economic and food security of our country, increasing the material well-being not only of rural workers, but also of the population of Uzbekistan as a whole, the fertility of our land, which is our priceless wealth, is an integral part of regularly improving its quality. is liq. Legume crops solve 3 tasks at the same time. First, it is considered an important factor for increasing grain production, secondly, it makes it possible to solve the fodder problem in livestock breeding, and finally, thirdly, it is a source of increasing soil fertility. Pea occupies a special place among such crops. As a result of the scientific research carried out by the scientists of our republic in the following years, it was possible to grow peas on irrigated land and get a good harvest. compared to when it is planted in dry farming, it is possible to collect the crop easily with the help of mechanization, as the tall pods are higher than the ground. (Z. S. Mustasnova 2023)

Methods and materials

The goal of our experiment was to observe the differences in the fertility of plants in different regions of Uzbekistan. For this, pea plants of the same variety were grown on soil samples from 12 regions for 40 days. The plants were placed in pots with 1 kg of soil and plant seeds were planted. "Polvon" pea variety was selected for the experiment. "Polvan variety is a selection variety of the Research Institute of Cereals and Legumes in irrigated lands. Authors of the variety: Mannopova M, Siddikov R, Abdurakhimova Sh. Belongs to the Carneum group. Large-seeded, 1000 seeds weigh 520.0 g. The variety is tall, on average 66-75 cm. The height of the first pod on the stalk is 23-28 cm, suitable for mechanical harvesting. Vegetation period is 122 days on average. Average productivity: 36.6 s/ha. Resistant to drought and pod cracking. The protein content is 28.0%. Since 2011, it has been included in the State Register for planting on irrigated lands of our Republic. It is recommended for planting in Jizzakh, Kashkadarya and Samarkand regions of our country.(agro .uz 2023)

Soils were brought from fields where different plants were planted from 12 regions.

№	Regions	District	Received date	The place where the soil was taken	Weight (kg)
1	Tashkent	Parkent	15.04.2023	Mosh o'rni	30
2	Bukhara	Qora ko'l	17.04.2023	Bean place	20
3	Farg'ona	Oltiariq	13.04.2023	Soya o'rni	25
4	Jizzakh	G'allarol	14.04.2023	No'xat o'rni	23
5	Khorazm	Urganch	15.04.2023	Loviya o'rni	22
6	Namangan	Uychi	13.04.2023	Mosh o'rni	25
7	Navoiy	Xatirchi	15.04.2023	No'xat o'rni	28
8	Kashkadarya	Dehqonobod	12.04.2023	Mosh o'rni	24
9	Andijon	Bo'ston	13.04.2023	Soya o'rni	26
10	Samarkand	Kattaqo'rg'on	14.04.2023	No'xat o'rni	30
11	Sirdaryo	Boyavut	15.04.2023	Soya o'rni	25
12	Surxondarya	Qumqo'rg'on	12.04.2023	Mosh o'rni	20

Pea seeds were soaked in water for 1 hour before planting, then 9-10 cm holes were dug in the pots and planted. Each pot contains 1 kg of medium moisture soil. Pea seeds were grown for 4 weeks at normal humidity after sowing.

After 4 weeks, the plants were removed from the pots and their biometric parameters were determined: plant height, root length, number of nodules, wet mass. After obtaining the biometric indicators, the soil where the plants were grown was taken and the amount of nutrients in the soil was analyzed and compared with the results of the preliminary analysis.

1 st table

Regions	Qayta-riqlar	Length (cm)	Fresh weight(g)	Dry weight(g)	N	P	K
Farg'ona	1	24	2	0.8			
	2	42	2.1	0.5			
	3	38	1.7	0.7			

Namangan	1	35	1.5	0.8			
	2	39	1.3	0.8			
	3	36	2	0.6			
Sirdaryo	1	27	1.8	0.6			
	2	42	3.6	1.1			
	3	45	3.2	1			
Toshkent	1	45	3.1	0.4			
	2	39	2.3	0.6			
	3	41	3	0.8			
Jizzax	1	45	4.2	1.6			
	2	37	2.4	1.2			
	3	47	4.8	1.7			
Samarqand	1	40	2.6	0.9			
	2	50	3.4	1.1			
	3	22	0.8	0.5			
Navoiy	1	33	1.4	0.2			
	2	26	1.2	0.8			
	3	49	2.6	1			
Buxoro	1	25	1.2	0.5			
	2	38	3	0.8			
	3	28	1.4	0.2			
Xorazm	1	32	1.5	0.3			
	2	32	1.5	0.4			
	3	33	1.5	0.8			
Qoraqalpoq	1	38	1.4	0.5			
	2	30	1.2	0.4			
	3	24	1	0.4			
Qashqadaryo	1	41	1.4	0.6			
	2	31	1.6	0.7			
	3	27	1.2	0.6			
Surxondaryo	1	42	2.1	0.7			
	2	48	2.4	0.9			
	3	43	2.1	1.1			

Results

The results obtained from the experiment show that the "Polvan" pea variety was taller in the soils brought from the southern regions of our country than the plants in the soils brought from the rest of the regions. As the experiments lasted for 4 weeks,

nodules were not formed on the plants. It was observed that the nodules appeared on the pea roots from the 5th week and unstressed conditions.

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